

Steel Structures in Times of Great Challenges

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ABSTRACT

The Multihall consists of three elements. We see them as thin, flat, and curved. Two of them are flat structural elements: a lower and a higher horizontal roof of folded plates. The higher element of the structure is a thick plate that can take bending while resting on the vertical cylindric wall. The cylinder is a curved shell. These three elements, the two plates and the curved shell, are three different structural and material details, but they are all stiff in their own plane, as if they were stitched together. And yes! from that came the idea, to compare the structure with a high hat. It needed no stiffeners and it seemed to swing in the air, as the hat of the storyteller H. Chr. Andersen. It can be carried on simple sticks below the cylinder, held together in the wind by stiches along the edge of the curved wall. It is dividing space in three directions, balancing horizontal reactions on the cylinder wall. Making the continuing construction stable.

Key Words: *Architecture, Structure, Buildability, Strength by form, Stiffness as Design Parameter*

fig. 7. top left: understandable for construction without structural stiffening, to the right, static explanation, three elements of the cylinder hat: brim · cylinder · upper brim

introduction ...

At the EURO Steel conference 2017 in Copenhagen, I presented the structural concept for the Multihall of Falkonergården Gymnasium Frederiksberg, in cooperation with MOE/*Artelia*, as structural engineer.(1)

The project was a result of an architectural competition won by *Falko Architects, prof. Tage Lyneborg, Høgni Hansen and Carl Th. Lyneborg*.

I was by them invited to formulate the structural concept, with Moe as responsible for the structural design. The Multihall had been positive received in architectural magazines, and won several prizes despite *its strange, complicated structure*.

During the following years I received inquiries from out-side the European area with recognitions and invitations for further development of my research work with this type of building research developed as illustrated by the building.

Analyzing this together with my colleague Ola Wedebrunn, with whom I have worked for years with architecture technology-science at the *Institute of Technology, the Royal Academy*, we decided to make this article for the Nordic Steel 2024.

Ole Vanggaard, Møn 2024

fig. 1. Steel construction in its own world. Meeting of cylinder wall and upper brim.

illustrations: Falkonergårdens Gymnasium Multihall

fig. 2. Upper steel plate during construction erected in only two days

fig. 3. left steel structure from exterior, undressed, right interior, columns, floor, walls and roof dressed in oak.

fig. 4. Multihall addition 2015 Falko Architects to school 1955, architect Thomas Havning, entrance to Multihall from East with cylinder dressed in cedar wood. photo, Laura Stamer

Structural Presumptions

The winning scheme from Falko Architects was very easy to read and to for the engineer as plane stiff plates, and a cylindrical closed silo wall. Sewn together along horizontal lines, stringer, between silo and high and low roof, and with the cylindrical truss wall vertically supported by 12 columns freely placed straight under the cylinder verticals. The columns minimized in dimension to increase the useful floor area. *fig.5*. The 12 columns nearly carry the total weight of the building! The lower roof nearly absorbs the total horizontal for the building, As a balancing fat bird with 12 legs!

fig. 5. Cross section elevation West, Falko Architects, from competition entry.

The plan should be exploited to the maximum. The three shear walls placed at the border of the hall, in concrete is responsibility for the total horizontal stability for the building. This means, that the building has a well determined support. Looking upon its steel structure as if it was shell dome supported with the 12 columns.

But it also means that you can see the roof shape of a *rigid high hat*, then you will have it stiff connected with horizontal bracing in, x-y direction, on the three outer walls and vertical support on the 12 columns.

fig. 6. Sketch, static principals from introduction

As Plate Structure

The three elements must be able to resist the forces and have what is called a *stable equilibrium*. The *silo* as a triangular folded plate, and the low roof as a solid concrete slab.

The top has two directions of girder beams, and the square is not stable, they can be squished by diagonally forces. But if there is a ring around them, then they can work as bicycle wheels. In the earlier article I showed how a small Swedish computer program *pointSketch* (2) that can be used to verify the stability of that body under different loads. So, it is easy to check with *graphical calculations*. It was difficult to convince the architect on that point, but it was accepted.

For us who have followed the concept of *plate structures*, it is just as natural as to analyze a pinned 2D structure – *a truss par example* – that control the stability, not only by the numbers, but also by their interactions, and you need no computer to find the answer! Sufficient to hand it over to a serious detailed calculation in another part of the engineering team.

So, *animating* the investigation or use bits of programs are two important assistances for a series conceptual concept. One more is using simple light cardboard models. Not as architectural models, but to check the stability.

Stability vs Rules

The concept for the structure will normally follow a structural calculation based on loads in relation to the forces – *action and reaction between members* – and the elastic deformations due to the stress in the member. This is how structural engineering has been used for more than hundred years. Structural members acting on each other. With the plate theory, you join the plate body along stringers, without any bending and secure that the whole body is stiff.

It is in a way the same process, as you have, if you analyze a 2D girder beam. Only this time it is in 3D. You do not involve the elastic deformation, only check that the stability of the bodies that is many times larger, than the stiffness of the simple members. It is not new statics. It is a very simple way to control stiffness. In the appendix, you will find a more precise definition, but it is not deep math. Just a way to deal with the 3 dimensions.

We think that the use and development of how to make a simple judge of the stability of a building structure, is necessary to learn to work with, to make the structure follow the demand for a better use of our resources. It is possible in steel, but it will demand more holistic view of the structure. You will presumably not gain enough if you do not find a new and creative way of work with the conceptual design.

By using simple calculations, and methods like the plate theory you can investigate and make a realistic judge of possible solutions before you invest in a *finite element* calculation.

The large computers, and their ability to fulfill the growing bureaucratic demands in building design, will seldom find, what we have not done before. Neither IT– or IA– in Neural networks, will find developments fast as we need. We need to use the human brain where it is best: In creation, art and in creating methodic and theories. *In this article we have pointed upon some relations to search for new ways. The Unexploited plate theory, and the use of what we see in nature.*

History of Stability of Plate Structures

The mathematical description of plate theory has been used for nearly 100 years in Denmark. What we didn't know was, that it was rarely used worldwide.

The origin for the structural principle of plate structures were formulated in the instruction SBI 82, 1976, published by the State Building Research Institute, based on notes from lectures given by engineer professor Jørgen Nielsen in the nineteen seventies. It was edited as official direction for simple calculation of structural plates. *fig. 6*. Actual, the father of Jørgen Nielsen, Dr. tech N.J. Nielsen was engineer for the first larger concrete plate structure in Denmark, the Fønnesbech building in the Centre of Copenhagen in situ concrete about 1935.

The formulations are quoted from the English edition of SBI Direction 115, 1981, *Stability of Plate Structures*, the official translation of the original SBI 82 instruction.

The direct formulation of the Direction are:

On the concept of "plate structures"

Walls and slabs are much stiffer, when they act as plates than when they act as slabs

The original text is about real plate units in multi-story buildings. They are in SBI 82 to include members in *stable equilibrium* as single curved shell units and as cylindric walls, corresponding to the *silo* of walls of the Falkonergården central space. That is why bending normally can be ignored in the estimate of the stability. The formulations are based on the English edition of SBI Direction 115.

On the concept of "stability"

A building is said to be stable when its individual members

- 1) *are in stable equilibrium, and*
- 2) *can resist the forces acting on them.*

A structural member is in stable equilibrium when positive work is required to move it. If, on the other hand, positive work is not required to achieve such movement, the member is said to be movable, see figure 3. When all the members of a structural system are in equilibrium, the building itself is also in stable equilibrium.(3)

fig. 6. illustration fig. 3. from SBI Direction 115

BUT: Real building is not the same as experimental building. Despite that they can assist the development for a better use of resources in the building industry. It

is particularly important when it comes to *steel*, to understand that it is a *high value* product – to be aware of the value.

The Multihall is real. The origin of the structural design is not based upon a usual logic, where the structure is built on simple principles following the scientific development and assumptions of the last two centuries.

The brilliant architectural values and design which the Multihall has been praised for, has opened for structural solutions, using a theoretical approach different from the usual structural theory.

Seen in the near IT– future, it is important to make it clear that although the use AI–, neural and genetic networks is possible, this only gives us a limited value. The reasons are, that the basic assumptions for computer handling are the physics created in the post 1800. This is a very unpopular statement.

Summary

The Multihall, is a steel structure dressed in wood, cedar in the exterior and oak in the interior. Thus, steel is consciously invisible – *in its own world*.

At the time of construction, we saw this as a great structural advantage as a natural reference to how tree trunks have a completely different functionality compared to the productional leaves. An optimization of strong materials due to millions of years of genetic design.

Nature has always been an inspiration for Architecture. We have tendency to integrate all the functions of the building components in mechanical and electrical components. Most other parts of the building have a shorter lifetime than the structure, like the leaves and flowers. It is natural to see the surfaces of wood on the outside, but it is strange to see an internal ceiling structures of the wooden veneer, shaped to pretend to be wide timber beams hiding a slender steel structure. This is the case in the Multihall. May be that is where the *strange, complicated structure* comes from!

In the project group we found a rational approach to steel *hanging* from the structure. This is the leading theme of the structure in the Multihall, others are the integration of 3D understanding of the structural body and the use of two-dimensional stiff foldable *membranes*, which obviously has much larger stiffness and strength than what would have been achieved from usual structural assemblies of blocks and rods. The conceptual judgement and the safety of structure uses the term *stiff structure*, defined in Direction for *Stability of Plate Structures*, by SBI, the Danish Building Research Institute. These principles as described above, are used in several built structures in Denmark and abroad. It gives a direct assistance for the preliminary assessment of structures. The Multihall, has been followed by conventional digital calculation elastic and plastic, for safety according to certified rules in the final structural report.

fig. 8. Plate structure in stereometric space; Carceri, Giovanni Battista Piranesi, 18th century, collage 2024 Ola Wedebrunn. Time is past and future technology. Plate structure has a different response to gravity in space. The collage is inspired by Archigram, Ron Herron and David Green, Living Pod 1966

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pointSketch: Pierre Olsson, Karl-Gunnar Olsson and more www.Chalmers.se

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Ola and Ole are colleagues from teaching, and research at the Royal Academy, Ola was not involved in the work of the Multihall 2015. Ole Vanggaard is the conceptual design engineer and together with Ola the author of the analysis of the Multihall, in 2024.

Notes:

(1) Chr. Weidemann, engineer of MOE.

(2) *pointSketch*: Pierre Olsson, Karl-Gunnar Olsson and more www.Chalmers.se

(3) SBI 82, 1976 and SBI Directions 115, 1981